

Multidisciplinary Optimization of Strut-Braced Wings with Distributed Electric Propulsion for Local Air Quality and Noise Improvements

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The INDIGO project, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, investigates innovative aircraft configurations aimed at reducing aviation’s environmental footprint. This study focuses on the conceptual design of a midrange aircraft featuring Large Aspect-Ratio Wings (LARW) and Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP), evaluated using a comprehensive Multi-Disciplinary Analysis and Optimization (MDAO) framework. The framework integrates models for aerodynamics, structural weight, powertrain performance, and noise, enabling optimization across competing objectives such as fuel efficiency, local air quality, and noise impact on airport vicinities. Preliminary results demonstrate the potential of LARW-DHEP to significantly reduce emissions and noise, particularly during low-altitude operations where aviation’s environmental impact is most pronounced. This study underscores the role of advanced MDAO techniques and novel propulsion architectures in advancing the sustainability of next-generation aircraft, contributing to global efforts to achieve carbon neutrality in aviation.

I. Introduction

ACHIEVING climate neutrality in aviation requires transformative advancements in aircraft technologies and operational concepts. To address aviation’s environmental impact, particularly on Local Air Quality and Noise (LAQN) in airport vicinities, a synergistic approach integrating aircraft and airport interventions is essential. Pollutants and noise emissions near airports have been linked to significant health and environmental concerns, underlining the need for innovative, sustainable solutions.

A. The INDIGO Project

The INDIGO (INtegration and Digital demonstration of low-emission aircraft technologies and airport Operations [1]) project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme, brings together leading academic and research institutions with airport stakeholders to develop novel aircraft concepts aimed at mitigating aviation’s local environmental impact. At the project’s core is a midrange aircraft concept featuring Large Aspect-Ratio Wings (LARW) and Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP). This aircraft is designed to operate in low-emission or fully electric modes near airports, reducing pollutants and noise, while relying on conventional fuels only when necessary, such as during cruise for battery recharging.

The INDIGO consortium, led by Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M), includes prominent European partners and operates over a 36-month timeline. The partners are Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali SCPA (CIRA), Ruhr-Universitaet Bochum (RUB), Technische Universitaet Braunschweig (TUB), Barcelona Supercomputing Center Centro Nacional De Supercomputacion (BSC-CNS), Deutsches Zentrum Fur Luft - Und Raumfahrt Ev (DLR), Centro De Referencia Investigacion Desarrollo E Innovacion Atm (CRIDA), Starptautiska Lidosta Riga Airport (RIGA), University Of Bristol (UoB) and University Of Strathclyde (UST). The overall funding was of 4.4 million euros (including 1.3 million euros from UKRI). The novelty in the three dimensions of powertrain, airframe, and operations demands an early-stage integration of these aspects into the design process. To address this, the INDIGO project employs a systematic Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) methodology for the development of the LARW-DHEP aircraft.

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B. Reference aircraft

The potential to improve LAQN is maximized when LARW-DHEP aircraft are deployed for missions that dominate current flight operations, typically mid-range routes of approximately 1000 nm. These routes are primarily operated by aircraft such as the Airbus A320 and Boeing 737.

Specification	INDIGO	A320	Specification	INDIGO	A320
MTOW	79 t	79 t	MPW	20 t	20 t
Wing Area	122.6 m ²	122.6 m ²	Range @ Max Payload	1000 nm	~2000-2500 nm
Cruise altitude	8000 m	~11000 m	Mach @ cruise	0.6	0.78

Table 1 Comparison of INDIGO and A320 specifications.

For the INDIGO project, the Airbus A320 serves as the reference aircraft, with specifications derived from open literature, including a Maximum Payload Weight (MPW) of 20 tons and a Maximum Takeoff Weight (MTOW) of 79 tons (see table 1). The INDIGO LARW-DHEP aircraft is designed to match the A320 in terms of MTOW and MPW, while being optimized for a mission range of 1000 nm with a full payload. The wing area is retained, while the Aspect Ratio (AR) is determined through synthesis and optimization.

The shorter design mission, compared to the A320's original range, enables the use of propellers instead of turbofans, minimizing time penalties while achieving significant operational benefits.

C. Paper Overview

As part of the INDIGO project, one of the initial technical deliverables is the interim preliminary configuration of the LARW-DHEP aircraft. This configuration forms the foundation for (1) assessing LAQN indices under current and projected air traffic scenarios at European airports, and (2) facilitating iterative refinements in the aircraft design process.

This paper outlines the methodology and presents the initial findings of the INDIGO aircraft design, with a focus on the sustainability advantages of the LARW-DHEP architecture. The paper begins with a description of the modeling approach and MDO framework, followed by a discussion of key optimization results, highlighting the potential of innovative configurations to enhance aviation's environmental sustainability.

II. Methodology

Designing an aircraft is a highly complex task, as various disciplines contribute to the process, often with competing objectives [2]. Achieving a balanced design requires reconciling these conflicting demands to meet practical and regulatory constraints while optimizing performance based on predefined criteria. For the INDIGO project, the primary focus is on improving LAQN in airport vicinities. This involves prioritizing designs that significantly reduce gaseous emissions and enhance aeroacoustic performance. While addressing emissions at the source is crucial, further improvements in pollutant concentrations in populated areas can be achieved by optimizing flight trajectories. However, maintaining competitive performance across the entire mission remains critical to ensure economic feasibility. Consequently, the challenge necessitates a multiobjective optimization approach that accounts for LAQ, noise, and block fuel efficiency.

The analyses conducted in this work leverage an enhanced version of the in-house MDO platform, MOTIVATION [3, 4]. Built on OpenMDAO [5], a Python-based framework for multidisciplinary optimization, MOTIVATION supports gradient-based optimization and the computation of total derivatives for complex models using object-oriented principles.

The subsequent sections provide a very brief overview of the modules specifically adapted for INDIGO's aircraft design. The interested reader can refer to works [4, 6] for more details.

A. The mission module

The mission module consists of two key sections. The first simulates a predefined mission profile, including climb, cruise, descent, a diversion at a lower altitude, and a 30-minute holding phase required for certification. Takeoff and landing segments are included under nominal conditions to assess fuel and/or energy consumption.

The second section evaluates critical performance metrics such as Takeoff Field Length (TOFL), Landing Field Length (LFL), and climb gradients under specified failure scenarios.

For the baseline mission, a range of 1000 nm is used, with a cruise altitude of 8000 meters and a Mach number of $M = 0.6$. Vertical and horizontal flight profiles were derived from radar data for DH8 aircraft at Riga Airport, modified to account for the INDIGO aircraft's higher wing loading. Aircraft dynamics are modeled for both airborne and ground phases. For airborne segments, the steady-state forces in the vertical and horizontal directions are balanced as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}_v = W \cos \gamma - q S_{ref} C_L = 0 \quad \mathcal{R}_h = T - W \sin \gamma - q S_{ref} C_D = 0 \quad (1)$$

For ground operations, the governing equation is:

$$m \frac{dV}{dt} = T - D - \mu(mg - L) \quad (2)$$

In these equations, S_{ref} is the reference wing area, W is the aircraft weight, T is thrust, D is drag, and γ is the climb angle. Thrust and power settings are adjusted for both nominal and failure scenarios to meet the performance objectives.

The full mission structure, including all segments and failure conditions, is illustrated in Figure 1. References [4, 6]

Fig. 1 Mission and segments. Reproduction from [3]

provide further details, and Figure 1, adapted from [3], offers a pictorial representation of all the segments considered in the mission module.

B. Airframe Modules

1. Aerodynamic module

The aerodynamic model balances accuracy with computational efficiency, enabling effective optimization during the conceptual design phase of the INDIGO aircraft. The methodology combines a Reduced-Order Model (ROM) derived from vortex-lattice method (VLM) simulations, semi-empirical flap-effect equations, and propeller blowing corrections (see Fig. 2a). The aerodynamic database, built using VSPAero [7], incorporates over 23000 cases sampled at angles of attack $(-5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ)$. A custom toolchain generates aerodynamic coefficients for lift and drag using radial basis function-based ROMs under a no-stall assumption.

Flap effects are modeled using generalized handbook data [8], while slipstream-induced corrections adapt aerodynamic coefficients in propeller-blown regions [9]. These corrections modify spanwise loading, and validation against VSPAero indicates errors below 10% for most cases. The aerodynamic module produces coefficients C_L and C_D as functions of key parameters such as propeller thrust T_i , propeller diameter D_i , and air density ρ .

Fig. 2 (a) Propeller-blown regions (from [9]). (b) Structural solutions with different hinges positions.

2. Weight module

The weight breakdown of the aircraft is expressed as:

$$OEW = W_{struct} + W_{sys} + W_{furnishing} + W_{operitems} + W_{ppsys} \quad (3)$$

Structural, system, and operational weights are derived using industry-standard methods [10–13] and NASA’s FLOPS [14]. The powerplant weights are based on data from INDIGO project partners. For the wing structure, regression formulas were developed to optimize weight distribution. Figure 2b illustrates the influence of hinge placement on structural efficiency, although these calibrations were not applied in this study.

C. Powerplant module

The powertrain architecture was selected based on a comprehensive review of hybrid propulsion systems, ultimately adopting a Parallel-Series Hybrid (PSH) topology, as shown in Figure 3. This configuration combines a parallel setup for inboard propellers, where gas turbines and electric machines share a common shaft, with a serial setup for outboard propellers driven by smaller electric motors. The approach minimizes energy losses and ensures operational flexibility, supporting both efficiency and performance across the flight envelope. In the parallel section, electric machines connected to the low-pressure shaft can operate as motors or generators, enabling dynamic power sharing between the propellers and the electrical system. This flexibility supports strategies such as providing additional thrust during climbs or optimizing cruise efficiency.

1. Powerplant component modeling

Turboshaft performance data, including Power-Specific Fuel Consumption (PSFC) curves, were provided by project partners [15]. Engine weight correlations were derived from reference [16] based on data from 130 engines.

Fig. 3 Parallel-Serial Hybrid architecture representation.

The electric architecture incorporates 2030 projections for power density [17]. Key efficiency maps for electric generators and motors were provided, enabling robust performance modeling despite the limited availability of data for larger machines.

Propeller performance was modeled using Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT), accounting for variations in blade geometry and disc loading. Performance maps provide aerodynamic characteristics over a range of operating conditions, ensuring accurate representation of distributed propulsion effects [15].

2. Overall powertrain modeling

The powertrain model simulates the performance of the hybrid propulsion system, defining the relationship between total thrust T and control variables for the inboard $\delta_{T_{IB}}$ and outboard $\delta_{T_{OB}}$ propellers. These throttles regulate the power delivered to the propellers by their respective components. The power delivered to the inboard ($P_{in,IBprop}$) and outboard ($P_{in,OBprop}$) propellers is expressed as:

$$P_{in,OBprop} = \delta_{T_{OB}} \cdot P_{max,ElectricMotorOB} \quad P_{in,IBprop} = \delta_{T_{IB}} \cdot P_{max,GearboxIB} \quad (4)$$

being $P_{max,GearboxIB}$ the maximum output power of the gearbox connected to the low-pressure turbine and $P_{max,ElectricMotorOB}$ the maximum output power of the outboard electric motors. The Power Fraction ψ links the inboard and outboard throttles, enabling dynamic thrust allocation, $\delta_{T_{OB}} = \psi \cdot \delta_{T_{IB}}$. Power sharing is managed via a local hybridization factor HF^* , determining the electric contribution to the inboard propeller.

$$HF^* = \frac{P_{out,EM}}{P_{in,IBprop}} \quad (5)$$

where $P_{out,EM}$ represents the output power of the electric motor, while $P_{in,IBprop}$ is the input power to the inboard propeller. Figure 4 illustrates the concept of local hybridization.

The powertrain combines direct shaft power from the gas turbine and electric energy from the batteries via an electric bus. The battery supplies power as needed or recharges when surplus energy is available. The total battery flow is given by:

$$P_{out,BATT} = 2 \cdot P_{OB} + 2 \cdot P_{in,I/R} \quad (6)$$

where P_{OB} and $P_{in,I/R}$ represent the power to and from the outboard inverters, respectively. Power flows are dynamically adjusted throughout the mission to optimize performance. For example, additional thrust from outboard propellers can support climb, while having the cruise phase relying primarily on inboard propellers for efficiency.

Fig. 4 Local hybridization factor HF^* .

3. Failure Cases

The integration of hybrid propulsion systems introduces additional complexity in failure modeling compared to conventional architectures. While traditional systems experience failures primarily at the engine level (e.g., propeller or core engine malfunctions), hybrid systems encounter further failure modes, such as distributed propulsor losses or malfunctions in electrical or thermal subsystems. In this work, failure scenarios are grouped into two categories: Lack of Thrust (loss of propulsive force) and Lack of Power (failure in power generation). These scenarios are depicted in Figure 5.

Lack of thrust Two critical scenarios are considered:

- FC1 Failure of an inboard propeller and its adjacent outboard counterpart, representing the most significant reduction in total thrust.
- FC2 Failure of the two outermost tip propellers, posing challenges for yaw control due to asymmetric thrust distribution.

These cases simulate worst-case conditions, such as bird strikes causing simultaneous blade-off events. While airworthiness standards for highly distributed propulsion systems remain undefined, these scenarios provide valuable insights into operational risks.

Lack of power Power generation failures are categorized as follows:

- FC3 Loss of the thermal engine, disabling turboshaft power while allowing electric motor operation.
- FC4 Loss of half the battery pack, reducing available electrical power.
- FC5 Electric motor failure, restricting the inboard propeller to thermal engine operation.

These scenarios highlight vulnerabilities unique to hybrid-electric systems and inform strategies for future certification norms.

Fig. 5 Powertrain failure cases FC1 to FC5.

Throttle settings During standard takeoff, throttles for inboard and outboard propellers are set to $\delta_{TOB} = \delta_{TIB} = 0.9$. In lack-of-thrust cases, throttles are increased to $\delta_{TOB} = \delta_{TIB} = 1$, maximizing available thrust. For lack-of-power

scenarios, the inboard throttle is fixed at $\delta_{TIB} = 1$, allowing electric components, which inherently possess a higher response rate, to adjust dynamically to available power.

D. Aeroacoustic Module

The IMMISplus tool, provided by DLR, supports initial aircraft design by delivering effective perceived noise level (EPNdB) metrics for take-off and approach trajectories. Enhanced with various propeller models, IMMISplus evaluates noise generated by distributed propellers across different power settings, sizes, and configurations.

A surrogate model based on Radial Basis Functions (RBF) was developed using this tool. To streamline input requirements and reduce training complexity, trajectory data, including thrust, shaft power, and speed, was sampled only at the start and end points of each flight phase. Intermediate values were interpolated, and the corresponding Effective Perceived Noise Level (EPNL) metrics were calculated according to ICAO Annex 16, Volume 1 guidelines [18].

This streamlined approach enables efficient noise evaluation for complex propulsion systems while maintaining compliance with regulatory standards.

E. The MDAO

The Multi-Disciplinary Analysis and Optimization (MDAO) framework is designed to maximize flexibility while minimizing pre-set assumptions, allowing for a comprehensive and unbiased exploration of the design space. This approach enables the identification of optimal configurations by leveraging interdisciplinary synergies to balance key objectives such as performance, efficiency, noise, and emissions. Such adaptability is especially critical for hybrid-electric and distributed propulsion systems, where the complexity of emerging technologies demands thorough design space exploration.

A notable aspect of this work is the use of a gradient-based optimization approach. While efficient, this method is sensitive to disruptions in the Multidisciplinary Analysis (MDA) process caused by operating outside model validity ranges, potentially leading to optimization failures. To address this, specific measures were implemented to improve the robustness of the MDA framework and ensure reliable convergence. The reader is referred to work [6] for details.

1. MDA

The MDA integrates key modules and ROMs for powerplant architecture, aerodynamics, structural weight, noise, and flight profile. These elements are tightly coupled in non-conventional architectures, resulting in implicit relationships that require numerical resolution to balance inputs, outputs, and additional state variables across disciplines.

A visual representation of the MDA arrangement for INDIGO's aircraft is shown in Figure 6. For each mission point, the trim equations are solved iteratively, requiring frequent interactions between aerodynamic and powertrain modules. Once resolved, outputs such as fuel flow and battery discharge rates are evaluated.

The implicit dependencies are resolved numerically alongside internal residual equations. Advanced MDAO techniques, including gradient-based Newton methods, are employed to handle these interactions. Analytical derivatives are applied to key modules, while finite-difference methods are used for ROMs, ensuring efficient optimization.

2. The MDO

The MDO framework is designed to explore the design space comprehensively, balancing performance, noise, and emissions to optimize hybrid-electric and distributed propulsion systems. It integrates the MDA framework and efficiently handles cross-disciplinary interactions.

An optimization problem is defined as minimizing an objective function $f(x)$, subject to equality and inequality constraints $c(x)$. Here, x represents the design variables (DVs). To ensure feasibility, constraints are imposed to address potential violations, such as battery State of Charge (SoC) dropping below zero or exceeding power component limits during optimization.

The objective function The objective balances three critical dimensions: LAQ, noise, and block fuel, expressed as:

$$obj = F^* + \alpha G^* + \beta N^* \quad (7)$$

where F^* represents normalized block fuel, G^* denotes fuel burn below 900 m as a proxy for gaseous emissions, and N^* quantifies non-dimensional noise (EPNL).

The design variables Design variables span wing planform, powerplant components, propeller characteristics, and mission-specific control parameters (e.g., hybridization factors HF^* and thrust distribution ψ). The full set exceeds 180

Fig. 6 A schematic of the MDA.

DVs, with key variables summarized in Table 2. This extensive parameterization allows fine-tuned control over design and operational characteristics.

Design variable	Units	Lower	Upper	Design variable	Units	Lower	Upper
Wing Planform							
AR	-	15	25	Taper ratio	-	0.31	0.33
Twist @ root	deg	-3	3	Twist @ tip	deg	-5	1
Twist @ strut	deg	-3	3	Strut chord	-	0.906	1.597
t/c @ root	-	12%	18%	t/c @ tip	-	9%	14%
Powerplant components							
Turboshaft rating	hp	3000	40000	Electric motor	hp	500	40000
Combination gearbox	hp	1000	100000	Inverter	hp	500	10000
Inverter/rectifier/gen.	hp	500	40000	Battery Weight	kg	10	100000
Inboard and Outboard Propellers							
Propeller IB dia.	m	1.5	5	Propeller OB dia.	m	1.5	5
Propeller IB TipM	-	0.5	0.78	Propeller OB TipM	-	0.5	0.78
Propeller IB solid_factor	-	0	1	Propeller OB solid_factor	-	0	1
Ground and flight phases							
HF^*	-	-20	1	HF^* (initial)	-	-20	1
HF^* (final)	-	-20	1	ψ (initial)	-	0.2	10
ψ (final)	-	0.2	10				

Table 2 Design variables and their bounds.

The constraints The constraints in the optimization framework are grouped into three main categories: Performance and Airworthiness, Geometric, and MDA Feasibility. *Performance constraints* include requirements for TOFL and Landing Field Length (LFL), which must not exceed 2,190 meters (equivalent to the A320). These lengths are evaluated under the various FCs and environmental conditions (e.g., dry/wet runways). Climb gradients must meet minimum

standards as defined by FAR-25 and CS-25 regulations. For hybrid configurations, the typical One Engine Inoperative (OEI) condition is replaced by the five FCs described earlier. Table 3 summarizes the requirements for different flight segments, including takeoff and go-around scenarios. Additionally, for FC2 (failure of adjacent outboard propellers), the yawing moment imbalance must remain within the aerodynamic limits of the rudder and vertical tail. This ensures that a 10° sideslip and rudder deflection can counteract the imbalance at stall speed (see Fig. 7). *Geometric constraints*

	Take-off			Go-around	
	1° segment	2° segment	3° segment	Approach	Landing
γ_{min}	0%	2.4%	1.2%	2.1%	3.2%
h_{ref}	35 [ft]	400 [ft]	1500 [ft]	-	-
Engine conf.	OEI	OEI	OEI	OEI	AEO
Power set	RTO	RTO	MCT	GA	-
Landing gear	Retraction	Retracted	Retracted	Retracted	Extended
Ref. speed	V_R	V_2	$1.45 V_{stall}$	-	-
Ref. weight	W. after $V_R - V_2$	W. after $V_R - V_2$	Segment end	MLW	MLW
Ground effect	Without	Without	Without	-	-
Flaps conf.	TO	TO	Clean	Approach	Landing

Table 3 Flight segments and configurations from FAR-25 for a twin-engine.

Fig. 7 Yaw constraint in FC2 case, with $\beta = \delta_t = 10^\circ$.

focus on propeller placement and clearances. The inboard propeller is fixed at 30% of the wingspan, while outboard propellers are distributed evenly along the remaining span. Two key geometric constraints are enforced:

- Propeller-to-Propeller Clearance: a minimum separation of 10% of the propeller diameter is required (Fig. 8a).
- Propeller-to-Ground Clearance: a minimum roll angle of 10° must be maintained during ground operations (Fig. 8b).

To ensure a feasible design, the MDA Feasibility constraints enforce that all components operate within their maximum capacity. Under failure scenarios, components can reach 100% of their rated capability, while nominal operations are capped at 90%. A crucial constraint involves the battery's SoC, which must remain above 20% to prevent degradation. This structured approach ensures compliance with performance, airworthiness, and geometric requirements while maintaining feasibility across all mission phases and scenarios.

It is important to highlight that the constraints monitoring specific responses throughout the mission generate numerous scalar constraints. This is due to the mission being segmented, with each segment further divided into up to 11 internal points for enhanced accuracy during equation integration. As a result, the optimization problems discussed in this paper involve approximately 5,500 constraints in total.

The optimizer The optimization process employed the Sequential Least Squares Programming (SLSQP) algorithm, as implemented in the *OpenMDAO* framework's *ScipyOptimizeDriver*, which leverages the *Scipy* library. This algorithm was selected for its ability to handle non-linear constraints and large numbers of design variables efficiently.

Fig. 8 Propeller clearances from the ground and neighboring propellers.

III. Optimization Campaign

The overall optimization campaign to select an interim INDIGO’s baseline, called IND1, comprises of two stages, as described in references [4, 6]. Whereas Stage 1 focused on exploring a wide range of design parameters (number of propellers, weights of the objective function, battery performances) through a Design of Experiment (DoE), Stage 2 refined the optimization by narrowing the focus to the number of outboard propellers.

A. Results

Stage 1 revealed a decoupling between prioritizing LAQ and noise metrics in the optimization process, with improvements in one metric minimally affecting the other. Prioritizing LAQ led to increased electric power utilization during takeoff and climb, emphasizing battery power density as a limiting factor, while prioritizing noise resulted in a more balanced thrust distribution among all propellers, albeit with higher fuel consumption due to energy conversion inefficiencies.

Stage 2 produced multiple optimal configurations, influenced by initial conditions and emphasizing different metrics (block fuel, LAQ, or noise). Due to observed multi-modality and time constraints, the IND1 configuration was selected based on its superior performance in LAQ and noise reduction, while still achieving notable block fuel efficiency improvements. Compared to the A320, IND1 demonstrates a 68% reduction in fuel burn below 900m, an 11.5 dB noise reduction, and a 30% decrease in block fuel consumption for identical payload and mission conditions (Table 4).

Metric	IND1	A320	Improv %
Block fuel [kg]	4530.5	6479.7	30.1
Fuel burn < 900m [kg]	72.4	227.6	68.2
Noise (EPNL) [dB]	74.9	86.4	11.5 dB

Table 4 Comparison of metrics between IND1 and the A320.

A rendering of the IND1 configuration is presented in Figure 9a, while the weight breakdown is depicted graphically in Figure 9b. Fig. 10 illustrates the optimal distribution of the IB propeller relative thrust, the normalized battery power output, and the total hybridization across the mission profile. Table 5 provides a summary of the key properties and data for the IND1 configuration.

IV. Conclusion

This study has outlined the conceptual design of a midrange aircraft incorporating Large Aspect-Ratio Wings (LARW) and Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP), as developed within the INDIGO project. Using a comprehensive Multi-Disciplinary Analysis and Optimization (MDAO) framework, the research has demonstrated the potential for advanced propulsion and airframe technologies to deliver meaningful environmental benefits.

Preliminary findings highlight significant reductions in fuel burn, emissions, and noise during critical low-altitude operations, addressing key sustainability challenges such as local air quality and noise pollution near airports.

Future efforts will aim to (1) enhance model fidelity across disciplines, (2) improve framework robustness through

Fig. 9 IND1: rendering and weight breakdown.

Fig. 10 Optimal distributions along the mission.

Variable	Units	Value	Variable	Units	Value	Variable	Units	Value
Prop. IB dia.	m	5.0	Comb. gearbox wt.	kg	103.4	Wing root twist	deg	-3.0
Prop. OB dia.	m	4.0	Aspect ratio	-	21.6	Wing tip twist	deg	-5.0
Prop. IB Mach	-	0.6	Taper ratio	-	0.4	Strut twist	deg	1.6
Prop. OB Mach	-	0.6	Strut chord	m	1.6	Root t/c	-	0.2
Prop. IB solid frac.	-	0.7	Inverter rating	MW	1.7	Tip t/c	-	0.1
Prop. OB solid frac.	-	0.3	Inv. rect. rating	MW	1.8	Block fuel	kg	4530.4
Engine rating	MW	6.7	Elec. motor rating	MW	1.6	Battery weight	kg	9215.8
Gearbox rating	MW	2.0	Inverter weight	kg	94.1	OEW	kg	43871.7
Inv. rect. motor wt.	kg	196.0	Wing weight	kg	13577.7	Engine weight	kg	1547.6
Motor weight	kg	79.2	Fuel burn <900m	kg	72.4	Mean EPNL	dB	74.9

Table 5 IND1 data.

global optimization techniques, (3) incorporate robust optimization under uncertainty with diverse trajectory sets, and (4) include pollutant concentration metrics for highly populated airport areas.

The results emphasize the value of integrated design approaches in advancing the development of sustainable, efficient, next-generation aircraft.

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